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SELF MANAGEMENT AS THE KEY TO THE SUCCESS OF A MODERN HEALTH MANAGER

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Highlights the essence of the concept of “self-management” and provides its author's interpretation. The goals and objectives of self-management in general and separately in the field of health care are considered. It was found that in order to effectively manage the staff of a health care institution, the manager, first of all, needs to know the science and art of self-management. General and local principles of science and practice of self-management are indicated.

The aim of the article is to develop and analyze the main features of self-management as the basis of success of a modern health care manager.

Materials and research methods are general scientific research methods such as systems analysis, comparison, generalization, swat analysis, forecasting. Studying the already studied components of the selected topic, such research methods as generalization, comparison, systems analysis were used. The basis for the study were the works of domestic and foreign scientists.

Results: the article establishes that self-management helps the leader: rationally organize their work and the work of their subordinates; realize professional and life goals; avoid stressful situations; increase efficiency; enjoy the work done. An analysis of the scientific literature has led to the conclusion that strong leadership is important to ensure the success of any medical institution. A manager who pays due attention to self-development is the key to the success of a healthy atmosphere in the team. Research indicates a high level of professionalism and creativity achieved by managers only when they have a need for professional self-development, self-improvement, as well as when they show a motivational and value attitude to themselves as a subject of medical activity.

Conclusions. Summarizing the above, it should be emphasized that self-management certainly affects the development of the modern manager of health care, so the following suggestions for the implementation of this method: to overcome administrative barriers to maintaining old management methods; to avoid problems caused by the inertial nature of public consciousness; reduce the level of conflict in the team; to overcome differences in professional competence; instill immunity to the fear of sanctions of the team - ridicule, overt and covert condemnation, ignorance

Keywords: health care system, management, manager, self-management, self-government, self-realization, self-education

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1. Introduction

The success of the healthcare system is, largely ensured by the stability and efficiency of medical institutions, organizational structures of this system. Medicine is an area of interaction of subjects not only the tried Doctor-Nurse-Patient, but other loaded systems of relations, Doctor-Patient, Doctor-Doctor, Doctor-Manager, Doctor-Nurse, Nurse-Patient etc. The success and effectiveness of professional interaction is ultimately ensured by the professionalism of the medical staff, motivation of employees, satisfaction with professional activities, competence of the head, and the literacy of building a management system.

Mastering the management tools of Ukrainian health care institutions is gradually creating a cultural basis for the introduction of such a method of management as self-management.

Self-Management and self-government organically include self-development, self-education, self-organization, self-control, self-analysis and self-evaluation.

As a result, it contributes to the formation as different from the previous ideas of the performance of work tasks. This method makes the work more conscious and gives it more creative features.

Thus, the work of the manager of a health care institution, based on self-organization, leads to self-realization of the object of management.

Sociocentric motivation, i.e., awareness of the importance of their work, makes it as effective as possible. The method of self-government testifies to the substantive part of the self-regulation of the institution as a complex technical, economic and social system.

Self-management involves independent choice, modern manager goals and ways to achieve them, active participation of staff in decision-making and implementation. Self-government involves not only the choice and independent decision-making, but also their mandatory implementation.

As a result, self-management, as a basis for improving the efficiency of management activities of the manager of the health care institution, allows you to manage yourself, your team and production processes effectively and efficiently.

This article was preceded by a thorough analysis of several scientific papers and publications that studied aspects of management in the health care system of Ukraine, in Ukrainian and American health care institutions, the role of leader and self-management as the main aspect of success. Scientists [1] which studied the organizational components of the manager's work identified their main components that increase the efficiency of the manager's work; [2] in their works described the main problems of management in health care facilities of Ukraine, which were at the time of 2017, as well as potential problems that are relevant today. [3] in his works studied the American style of management, its main features and benefits. In the works of [4] studied the effective model of management on the model of the American and [5] who in his work studied the effectiveness of management and self-education of employees of the American medical company.

These studies are relevant in modern conditions for the study of self-management as a basis for improving the effectiveness of managerial management.

The aim of the article is the development and analysis of the main features of self-management as a basis success of the modern manager of the health care institution.

2. Materials and methods

During the work, a number of both general and special methods of scientific knowledge were used: the logical-semantic method was used to clarify the essence and significance of institutional and economic aspects in the implementation of reforms in the field of health care in Ukraine; the method of structural analysis was used in the study of hospital districts and their powers and responsibilities as subjects of public administration in the field of health care; analytical method provided an opportunity to summarize the experience of institutional and economic aspects of health care reforms in Ukraine.

3. Results

Today in the scientific literature there are different views on the concept of self-management, some of them are listed further.

In most sources, self-management is defined as self-government, the process of self-activity, the elevation of personality. Effective self-government policy is objectively related to human nature (biorhythms, genetic program) and organization aspects (things, people, ideas, relationships), social management [1, 2].

Narrow interpretation of self-management as an individual technology for the use of working time is quite common. From the point of view of the scientist, L.

Seivert, self-management is a consistent and purposeful use of proven practical methods of work in everyday activities to use their time optimally and meaningfully. There is an obvious focus on such an area of self-management as time management.

The textbook of MSU scientists gives the following definition: self-management is the management of basic resources of the individual, activity, solvency, education. Here you could identify the resource approach to the subject of self-management research.

Self-management as a system of activities that allows one to make the most of their own capabilities, consciously and rationally manage their lives, actively and effectively influence external circumstances at work and in personal life for their own purposes.

In this definition, self-management is a technology that allows you to apply the methods of general management to the professional activities and personal activities of each person.

A similar approach to the concept of self-management could be traced in the definition of PG Breaks: self-management is a consistent and purposeful use of effective methods of work in everyday practice, with optimal use of their resources to achieve their own goals [3].

Self-management is the self-development of the manager as a person and the organization of his personal activities. It implies purposeful and consistent use of proven methods of work in everyday practice. The main goals of self-management include:

1. Maximum use of time and opportunities by the manager;
2. Conscious management of the life flow;
3. Overcoming external circumstances both at work and in personal life [4].

Self-management, above all, is self-organization, the ability to manage themselves, to manage the management process in the broadest sense of the word – in time, space, communication, business world. The main goal of self-management is to make the most of their own capabilities, consciously manage the course of their lives (self-determination) and overcome external circumstances both at work and in personal life.

In this definition, the emphasis is on such a management function as the organization of activities (self-organization), although the composition of management functions, as shown above, is much broader. Most likely, these functions are implemented by the subject in one way or another in the process of self-government and deserve attention within the discipline “Self-management”.

Given the theoretical analysis of the interpretation of the concept of self-management, from our point of view, is the implementation of the functions and achievements of science and management practice in relation to themselves and their own lives.

The subject of knowledge, the researcher, yourself, the object, also you and your life, the subject, the aspects of your life and your qualities as a professional and a person, in the context of different life situations and activities. The problem is the discrepancy between the realities of life, activities, results, achievements and desires, expectations of success and achievement.

The main purpose of self-management is to maximize and develop their own capabilities (potential) of the subject and influence the factors of development, consciously manage their lives (self-determination) and use favourable and overcome adverse external circumstances at work and in personal life. It is a question of how to increase efficiency of activity of the worker, for the head, to increase efficiency of management of collective and personal efficiency, being aware of factors of efficiency and constantly and competently being engaged in self-improvement.

Note that the tasks that are solved based on self-management could be defined as follows:

- Learn and effectively manage their own lives and work, use their strengths, minimize the impact of shortcomings;

- Successfully overcome the difficulties and problems that arise in the organization of their work, establishing communication with management, colleagues and subordinates;

- Maintain high efficiency and stress resistance;

- Effectively influence the work behaviour of individual employees and groups;

- Effectively solve problems related to work, both individually and using the potential of subordinate groups [5].

However, any social system in its natural development, at a certain time, reaches such a high level at which existing forms and methods of management exhaust adequate resources of intellectual and human resources.

Eventually, that requires the search for new forms and methods of management. Not in the framework of quantitative change of these forms and methods of management – their intensive development, but in the form of qualitative transformation as an intellectual component of the decision-making function [7].

Management is designed to create the conditions necessary for the successful operation of the organization and may assume that profit is not always the goal of existence, but the result of the company is ultimately determined by the market.

Profit creates certain guarantees for the future activities of the organization, as the accumulated income in the form of various funds reduces the likelihood of economic risks associated with the sale of goods in coexistence with an unstable environment as a constant source of risk [5].

Along with commercial, there are non-profit organizations that operate (public organizations, foundations, etc.), whose activities are aimed at achieving socio-cultural and managerial goals that could also be managed based on management principles.

- Direct personnel management of the organization;

- Management of production and market business activities of commercial (and non-commercial) health care organizations by hired managers involved by the owner (or himself, who acts as a manager);

- Management of production and economic activities of state health care institutions that provide medical services (except for several special structures - forensic medicine, penitentiary institutions, Ministry of Emergencies, etc.) [8].

In the last decade, interest in the problems of organization and management in health care has grown significantly around the world. One of the reasons for such attention of researchers and practitioners in the field of public health is the natural integration processes taking place in health care systems, the consolidation of structures, to some extent ensures the preservation and improvement of public health: hospitals, clinics, insurance and pharmaceutical companies, government agencies, social security institutions, etc. Processes characteristic both at the level of national health care systems and in the international sphere are noted [5].

Given the priority of economic components of state development, the unique nature of health care as part of the social structure of society is also manifested in the fact that institutions and actors of the healthcare system, being the largest employers, ensure economic stability, and as medical structures, bear an important share of responsibility for labour productivity, health of the nation, defense capabilities of the state.

Modern health care systems, functioning and developing in a liberal society, in the existence of civilized markets and specific marketing relationships, inevitably feel the impact of processes that characterize such relationships.

However, these processes of interaction are certainly two-way: health systems around the world are increasingly affected by market fluctuations and the integration of marketing and policy structures. Today, no country in the world could manage the health care system without considering the impact that could have on the organization and activities of this system of government, both domestic and global markets, both domestic and global population health status [9].

The road to improving the efficiency of health care as a system is primarily through improving the quality of management in the development of professionals themselves. Of course, the reforms of any country depend on the history of this country, on economic and social benefits, but even the initial consideration of reforms, not to mention their creation and implementation, should begin with a rethinking of the role and functions of management.

Also, the issues of health management are currently very relevant in connection with the commercialization of the industry, the decentralization of state power at the territorial level and because of increasing the level of independence of medical organizations (MO) [10].

The main goal of health management, of course, is to reduce society's losses from morbidity, disability, and mortality. To achieve this goal requires effective activities of the entire health care system and each individual medical organization, which requires the introduction of new principles and approaches, methods, and models of management of all parts of medical organizations of different forms of ownership, aimed at meeting such mutual related goals:

- Increasing the availability of quality and timely medical care;

- Improving the quality of life and health of the population;

- Increasing the profitability and profitability of the MoD [2].

Note that before trying to control others, one must learn to control oneself. In leadership development, we spend a lot of time talking about leadership and managing others. But leadership really begins when a manager could manage himself.

Self-management is sometimes described as emotional intelligence. It is the ability to understand and control what we feel (our emotions) and how we act (our response to those emotions). Today's managers who develop self-management skills need to know how their communication and actions affect others.

In 1999, Peter F. Drucker, considered by many to be the father of modern management theory, wrote a classic article for the Harvard Business Review entitled self-management. He noted that there have been naturally great achievements in life, and that most of us will need to learn to manage ourselves to be successful.

Peter F. Drucker identified five strategies to better into be:

1. Know your strengths. Drucker noted that most people do not identify their own strengths and weaknesses. He was an early supporter of the concept of leadership based on strengths. There are many ways to identify our strengths. One of the most powerful is to seek feedback from those we work with on a regular basis and those who monitor us.

2. Determine how you do everything. In his article, Drucker makes an important observation that few have ever analyzed how they get their job done. An important question that every leader should ask himself: are you a reader or a listener? Leaders need to understand how they best absorb information. Leaders also need to understand how they learn better. Do you need to write to get clarity on this issue or do you want to talk about the problem? Understanding your personal work habits is also crucial - do you work better alone or with others? Can you work under stress?

3. Understand your values. Drucker suggests that values should be the ultimate litmus test of whether a job is right for you or not. Does the culture of the organization, mission and strategic direction align with what you believe in your work? He suggests that they should not be the same, but they should be close enough to coexist. When your values conflict, it may be impossible to do your best.

4. Find out where you belong. Drucker acknowledged that finding out where you really belong in the world can be a challenge. According to him, a successful career is not planned, but develops when people are ready for opportunities and know their strengths.

5. Decide who you can contribute. The last question leaders need to ask themselves is their strengths, how they do things and their values – where could they make the greatest contribution? There are many opportunities presented to us throughout our careers, but they

will not all be right for us. When you do the work, you had to do, you will prosper [11].

In turn, health managers must have change management skills to adapt to this change in the industry. These vital skills will help them cope with the need for change in workplace processes and cultures, as well as communicate this need to health professionals at all levels. Legal knowledge may not seem like an obvious requirement for a healthcare manager, but it is important for working in today's medical environment.

Analytical skills help make healthcare facilities better. It is not enough for a manager to keep up with the status quo for real success. Successful managers look to the future, investing their analytical skills in the work to assess current operations and find areas for improvement [5].

The peculiarity of the modern vision of the manager as a group leader is that he is seen as one who has an innovative organizational culture, as the main initiator of subsequent changes in the institution. The most important characteristics of a modern manager, such as professionalism, the ability to lead a team, the desire to create and maintain a good psychological climate, are impossible without working on yourself, without self-management.

Therefore, we present some general and local principles of science and practice of self-management (Fig. 1).

Local principles of self-management are studied and implemented within individual areas of self-management. For example, the principle of priority in time management [1].

Problem-solving skills help managers overcome obstacles. No matter what the size of their organization, health managers call on their problem-solving skills daily. These talents come in handy in resolving personnel disputes, dealing with the health crisis, and balancing the budget.

Healthcare managers also rely on their problem-solving skills to identify weaknesses in their organizations. After using analytical skills to evaluate the processes and procedures of the company, to correct and improve the object you need to solve the problem of know-how [5].

Problem solving is a skill with many aspects, including staying objective, engaging in creativity, and encouraging the right open people to support. Practice all of this could help healthcare managers become experts in solving problems.

Today's healthcare managers do not just have to encourage the right people to solve problems. Joint management has become a key part of modern health management. Healthcare is shared, even in the world of private practice. Successful managers need to be open to sharing responsibilities with other key employees, including clinical leaders and front workers.

Fig. 1. General principles of science and practice of self-management. Source: compiled by the author based on [1, 5]

Technological skills help managers navigate modern jobs. Technological skills are becoming increasingly important for managers working in the field of health care. Most hospitals and healthcare facilities use electronic medical records, as well as specialized software for coding and invoicing. Mobile health programs are also on the rise. As technology advances, health managers must keep up with the latest initiatives.

4. Discussion of research results

If we compare our research with research that is currently available in the scientific literature of other scientists, we find that there are different views on the concept of self-management. In most sources, self-management is defined as self-government, the process of self-activity, the elevation of personality. Effective self-government is objectively related to human nature, social management [2, 5, 6, 12].

Narrow interpretation of self-management as an individual technology for the use of working time is quite common. From the point of view of the scientist L. Seivert, self-management is a consistent and purposeful use of proven practical methods of work in everyday activities to optimally and meaningfully use their time [4]. There is an obvious focus on such an area of self-management as time management. Also, one of the definitions is: self-management – is the management of basic resources of the individual, activity, solvency, education

[5]. Here you can identify the resource approach to the subject of self-management research.

Study limitations. Our research is focused on determining the self-management of the head of the health care institution, which requires consideration of the specifics of the profession (specialty, specialization) and many factors for effective management of the health care institution in pandemics and war.

Prospects for further research. Nevertheless, the issues of the mechanism of self-management organization at the level of the health care institution, at the level of the hospital district and finally at the state level remain open for further investigation. Topics of self-management of interns, practitioners and not only managers in the field of health care are also relevant for further research.

5. Conclusions

In summary, it should be noted that self-management affects development of a modern manager of a health care institution. To implement this method, you need:

- To overcome administrative obstacles, which are expressed in the preservation of old management methods;
- To avoid problems caused by the inertial nature of public consciousness;
- Reduce the level of conflict in the team;

– To overcome differences in professional competence;

– Instill immunity to the fear of sanctions of the team – ridicule, overt and covert condemnation, ignoring.

Also, rational management of own resources – goals, phases of activity, performance metrics, time and information are the key to the effectiveness of structures controlled by the manager. The task of the head as a subject of management is to organize their own work so that the effectiveness of the management of the health care institution was maximum.

Self-management practices are a tool that allows managers to build an effective self-management system as the most important resource in modern organizations. In addition, it allows you to perform tasks with minimal costs, as well as find time for self-education, creative development, and leisure. Its use will allow to solve the

set tasks effectively, and to avoid unforeseen difficulties and overloads,

Conflict of interests

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